

CURRENT STATE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. The article examines the problems and opportunities related to the current state of artificial intelligence in Uzbekistan. It will address issues such as data privacy, ethical considerations, and the need for skilled AI professionals. At the same time, the author highlights the potential for economic growth, job creation and community development through the strategic adoption of AI technologies.

Key words: artificial intelligence, information technology, AI technology, intelligent teaching systems, internet of things (IoT), national strategy, Self-learning methods.

Introduction. Artificial intelligence – what is it? The most complex entity in the world is man. The desire to understand the complexity of man has always existed and manifested itself in different forms. Now this has become even more relevant. The development of computer technology has led to the emergence of many works related to attempts to learn to recognize and synthesize human technical speech, create technical vision systems that can recognize people's faces no worse, and even better, than human eyes, teach cars to drive independently without a human driver, etc. Systems that exhibit human-like behavior are called artificial intelligence (AI) systems. In fact, the study of these systems is an independent scientific field that unites many scientific disciplines.

According to one definition, artificial intelligence is a science and technology that includes a set of tools that allow a computer, based on accumulated knowledge, to answer questions and make expert conclusions based on this, i.e. gain knowledge that was not included in it by the developers. The science called

“artificial intelligence” is part of the complex of computer sciences, and the technologies created on its basis belong to information technologies. There are many other definitions that are less resistant to criticism.

Accordingly, AI systems are defined as computer systems that use AI technologies in their work. Moreover, in most cases, the algorithm for solving the problem is unknown until the result is obtained [6,8].

AI systems are conventionally divided into two classes – strong (or general) AI and weak (or applied) AI. Let's define strong, or universal, artificial intelligence as AI comparable to human intelligence, i.e. AI that can learn like humans do and is as advanced as most humans, and in many ways even superior. There are many more strict definitions, but this definition is sufficient for understanding.

Materials and methods. All other systems, including the AI systems that surround us now, are called weak AI because they can only do one thing, such as searching for queries on the Internet, making a diagnosis for a specific disease, etc. The help of such AI makes life more comfortable and work more productive. Such systems will be increasingly improved in the near future; AI systems are already doing many specific types of work better than people. It should be noted that in the process of working on projects with weak AI, a huge amount of preparatory work is done.

Machines teach intelligent skills such as information retrieval, speech recognition, natural language processing, facial recognition, inference, etc. Individually, these are just powerful tools, but they are developing rapidly, pushing AI technologies forward year after year and bringing the creation of strong AI closer.

In connection with weak AI, mention should be made of the so-called AI effect (AI effect). It lies in the fact that as soon as a previously unimaginable result is actually achieved with the help of AI, then critics cease to consider such a task as an AI task, i.e. devalue its value. This effect is formulated in Larry Tesler's formula: «AI is everything that has not been done so far»[7,10].

To provide AI systems, scientists had to address such an issue as knowledge representation - this made it possible to create so-called expert systems (ES, systems that, based on knowledge bases, help in decision making); Self-learning methods for machines have become very important (intelligent teaching systems have appeared); attempts to replicate the functioning of the human nervous system. The latter resulted in the creation of artificial neural systems (ANN). Thus, the basis of all AI research is the idea of simulating human thinking processes using a computer. AI itself as a science belongs to the cognitive sciences, i.e. to sciences related to the acquisition (collection, accumulation, perception) of knowledge.

It is assumed that AI, comparable to human intelligence, will have an unlimited scope of application and will radically change our existence.

One of the questions for modern AI is whether this third wave will end with yet another disappointment and decline in interest in AI, or whether irreversible progress will be achieved in this field as a result of the current colossal efforts of the global scientific community.

According to the author, the stakes for AI are now very high and this area will develop intensively.

AI directions

The scientific discipline “Artificial Intelligence” is an umbrella one. Internally, AI is divided into many areas. Here are the main ones of them:

- Knowledge representation.
- Proof of theorems.
- Computer vision.
- Machine learning (knowledge acquisition, data analysis and hypothesis generation).
- Robotics.
- Natural language processing.
- Multi-agent systems.
- AI Tools.

Each of the listed branches of AI, in turn, is divided into dozens of other areas, especially robotics (several dozen areas).

As we see, due to the vastness of AI, it is impossible for a scientist to cover all its branches; specialization is required [6,9,10].

Main areas of work in the field of AI

Work in the field of AI is now underway in many countries and is being deployed on a wide front. They are grouped around the following areas.

1. Deep learning. Here, efforts are aimed at significantly reducing the training time of the neural network and reducing the size of the training sample. Ideally, the neural network should learn in real time.

2. The robot synthesizes answers based on the body of knowledge that was loaded into it, in relation to the context and sequence of words. The robot must learn to correlate incoming information with its knowledge base and learn [5].

3. Development of neuromorphic microcircuits and computers based on them. Such chips have already been produced by IBM and Intel corporations . So far they contain up to 4096 artificial neurons and up to 256 million synapses, but the direction is very promising.

4. Work will continue to map the human brain and model its functioning.

5. Development of speech recognition and understanding systems. Many services use a speech interface, which requires good speech recognition. Along with this, understanding what the user is saying is also important. In this regard, it is very important for such systems to understand the context of what is said, since context is the most important part of natural language. This part of the research is also moving towards developing systems that can interact with people through dialogue, rather than simply responding to stylized requests. Transmitting queries to search engines and a number of popular applications by voice, especially from smartphones, has already become commonplace, and the volume of such queries will only increase.

6. Development of brain-computer interfaces. The work that started rapidly in this direction has now slowed down, but will continue.

7. The study of systems of group behavior of robots and the interaction of robots and people during the performance of any operations. Research efforts are aimed at studying the efficient distribution of tasks between people and machines. This direction is important both for military robots and service robots, as well as for the manufacturing sector.

8. The introduction of AI in the Internet of Things (IoT), Industry 4.0 and other modern trends such as the digital economy, since processing the huge volumes of data generated in such systems without AI will face great difficulties.

9. Navigation of autonomous vehicles in the human environment. This most promising direction from a market point of view should ensure the beginning of widespread implementation starting from 2022–2025. driverless cars and cars in which the driver's actions are fully controlled by an autonomous driving system.

10. It is possible to develop a completely new class of systems such as “human intelligence on demand”, robotic services on demand (RaaS), etc.

11. Hyper-personalization of services. Since the user is now constantly connected to the network, based on his past data and behavior model, AI applications will have to be able to make assumptions about what services should be offered to him in given circumstances, what solutions will be optimal for him.

12. Combating the effect of “catastrophic forgetting”. When an AI system encounters something it has never been trained for, without retraining it will continually repeat the same mistakes. An attempt to retrain today's systems leads to a phenomenon called “catastrophic forgetting,” i.e. to a situation where learning a new subject violates the knowledge of previously learned things [6].

13. Development of a regulatory framework for the use of robots. “Robots as subjects of law have not yet been legally formalized in any country in the world, since for this it is necessary to officially recognize that a robot is not just a thing, but a creation endowed with, albeit artificial, intelligence, as well as its own will.

Therefore, there are no laws in the world that prescribe anything or directly prohibit robots. Legislators are faced with a far from simple task - to ensure a balance between the interests of technological progress, the security of society and the state, and the needs of an individual. In South Korea, in 2008, the “Law on Promoting the Development and Dissemination of Smart Robots” was adopted. In February 2017, the European Parliament adopted a resolution Civil Law Rules on Robotics – Civil law rules on robotics [5].

14. Development of such areas as understanding the text, reasoning based on precedents, etc.

According to a number of experts, current developments in the field of AI lack the hardware and software means of physical contact with the outside world in order to develop an understanding of the differences or similarities between the virtual and real worlds. This direction is developing in robotics, for example, the tactile surface of robot hands.

Trends in the use of AI systems in public administration

1. AI is most in demand in law enforcement agencies, as it allows the police to analyze video from many cameras in cities and search for criminals. Computer programs are capable of generating documents for the prosecutor's office and indictments themselves.

2. AI can have a major impact on traffic control and management in cities. In a number of countries such work is already underway.

3. AI for the Ministry of Emergency Situations. For example, manage the work of firefighters, predict the development of a fire.

4. Applications in AI in the judicial system. Assistant referees.

5. Analysis of social networks to prevent possible anti-state actions of radical groups.

6. In education – tracking the progress of each student, targeted assistance in planning education and career.

7. AI in government decision support systems in economics and banking.

8. Other.

The development of artificial intelligence technologies is accompanied by an increase in public and private investment. National strategy for the development of artificial intelligence. According to forecasts for the long-term socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in the case of insufficient development and use of competitive artificial intelligence technologies, the implementation of priority areas of scientific and technological development of the country will slow down, which will subsequently entail its economic and technological lag behind other countries. By Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 17, 2021 No. 4996 “On the development of artificial intelligence in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, the “National Strategy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence” was approved

intelligence for the period until 2030" (hereinafter referred to as the Strategy)[4]. The goals of the Strategy are:

- ensuring the accelerated development of artificial intelligence for the Republic of Uzbekistan to join the group of world leaders in the global artificial intelligence market;
- create opportunities to dominate the market and gain long-term competitive advantages;
- maintain the country's technological independence and competitiveness.

To develop artificial intelligence technologies, it is necessary to give priority to relevant scientific research,

Which should be aimed at creating completely new scientific results, including the creation of universal (strong) artificial intelligence. It requires the creation of a regulatory framework that ensures the protection of data obtained in the course of economic and scientific activities, including their storage primarily on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the establishment of priority access to such data as State bodies and organizations of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1,2].

CONCLUSION. By 2030, the volume of datasets published on public platforms should be sufficient to address all current AI issues, including through the publication of audio, speech, medical, meteorological, industrial and video surveillance data.

A comprehensive system for regulating social relations arising in connection with the development and use of artificial intelligence technologies must be created.

The main directions of creating the system are:

➤ ensuring favorable legal conditions (including through the creation of an experimental legal regime) for access to data, mainly anonymized, including data collected by government agencies and medical organizations;

➤ providing special conditions (modes) for access to data, including personal data, for the purpose of conducting scientific research, creating artificial intelligence technologies and developing technological solutions based on them;

➤ creating legal conditions and establishing procedures for simplified verification and implementation of technological solutions developed on the basis of artificial intelligence, as well as transferring the ability to make individual decisions to information systems operating on the basis of artificial intelligence (with the exception of decisions that may violate the rights and legitimate interests of citizens), even when government bodies perform state tasks (with the exception of tasks aimed at ensuring the security of the population and the state);

➤ elimination of administrative obstacles to the export of civilian products (construction, services) created on the basis of artificial intelligence;

➤ creation of unified systems for standardization and conformity assessment of technological solutions developed on the basis of artificial intelligence, development of international cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan on standardization issues, ensuring the possibility of certification of products (works, services) created on the basis of artificial intelligence;

➤ stimulating the attraction of investments, improving the mechanisms for joint participation of investors and the state in projects related to the development of artificial intelligence technologies, as well as providing targeted financial support to organizations involved in the development and implementation of artificial intelligence technologies (provided that the introduction of such technologies will bring a significant positive effect in the industry economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan);

➤ development of ethical principles for human interaction with artificial intelligence.

By 2025, the legal conditions necessary to achieve the goals, solve problems and actions provided for by the Strategy should be created, and by 2030, the Republic of Uzbekistan should have a flexible system of legal regulation in the field of artificial intelligence, including guaranteeing the safety of the population and aimed at stimulating development of artificial intelligence technologies [2,4].

In conclusion, this article provides a valuable overview of the status quo of AI in the Republic of Uzbekistan. By examining both the achievements and challenges, it offers a balanced perspective on the country's journey towards becoming a regional hub for AI innovation. Researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders will find this annotation to be a useful resource for understanding the multifaceted dimensions of the current AI landscape in Uzbekistan.

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